

Development of Emerging Technologies and Innovations through Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Programmes in Nigeria

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Abstract

This article is an opinion paper which deals with managing and development of emerging technologies and innovations through technical and vocational education and training (TVET) programmes in Nigeria. It examined the concepts of technical and vocational education, innovation and management, objectives of technical/vocational education in Nigeria as entrenched in the National Policy of Education 2014. The paper looked at the historical perspective of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. The challenges of technical and vocational education include: Inadequate funding, parental attitude towards technical towards technical and vocational education in Nigeria, shortage of teaching staff and curriculum content. Provision of qualitative technical and vocational education is necessary for technical education to achieve its aim. Based on that, recommendation/Strategies for ensuring technical and vocational education were made which include emerging technologies and innovations for improved funding of technical and vocational education; there should be a change in parental attitude towards technical and vocational education, recruitment of qualified manpower and improved curricula content.

Keywords: Technical and vocational education, management and development.

Introduction

Education all over the world have been viewed as a tool for both personal and national development (FRN, 2004). It is the process of receiving or giving systematic instruction, especially at the secondary or University education levels. Therefore, Education focuses on the training and developing of knowledge, skills, mind and character of the people for maximum productivity. Education facilitates the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, morals, beliefs and habits. It is adjudged, globally as an important instrument for socio-economic development of human skills, knowledge and attitude (Osim, 2022). Hence, education in Nigeria is an instrument par excellence for affecting national development FRN, 2014.

The Concept of Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Education in Nigeria

The development of human resources is one of the main factors in achieving sustainable economic and social development. TVET Education is described as the aspect of education which is concerned with the preparation of skilled manpower. It is a form of education, training and retraining which is directed towards developing the learner to become productive in a paid employment or in a self-employment (Marope, et. al., 2015). It can also be seen as that skilled based programme designed for sub professional level of education and based on a specific vocation. NPF (2014) notes that it is a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Consequently.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines TVET as that aspect of education which utilizes scientific knowledge in the acquisition of practical and applied skills in solving technical problems. Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) requires the inculcation of practice and learnt experiences in real life. The National Policy on Education (NPE 2014) considered Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as an integral part of general education in Nigeria that is beyond compulsory education but excluding degree-level programmes, which provides individual with occupational or work-related knowledge and skills. It empowers individual's organization,

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enterprises and communities and foster employment, decent work and lifelong learning thereby promoting inclusive and sustainable economic growth and competitiveness social equity and environment sustainability.

In other words, TVET is a type of education that is designed to prepare learners for specific careers and trades. This type of education is offered at the post-secondary or tertiary levels of education. They typically include both classroom instructions and practical training education used as a comprehensive term. Marope, Chakroun and Holmes, (2015) define Technical, Vocational Education and Training as that which provides practical skills, knowledge and technology for knowledge based and transition societies to be skillfully employed.

National Policy of Education (2014) highlights the goals of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) shall be to;

1. Provide trained man power in applied sciences, technology and business, particularly at craft, advance craft and technical levels.
2. Provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial and economic development.
3. Give training and impact the necessary skills to the individuals for economic self-reliance.

It is generally believed that one of the major parameters for measuring a country's economic growth and development and self-reliant is the extent of the technical education it has.

Concept of Management of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Program in Nigeria

Education is seen as the process of coordinating human effort towards the actualization of broad and specific goals of an organization while management is the act of applying the general processes and procedures to achieve the goals set for an organization. Hence, management is the process, which empowers, directs and motivates organizations to set and achieve their objectives by planning, organizing, directing and controlling their human and material resources meaningfully. Nzegbulem and Onyeagbako, (2019) define management as a kind of work a manager performs to enable people work effectively together. Therefore, management and development of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET), through emerging technologies and innovations simply put is the ability to manage technical and vocational education effectively. For Nwankwo (2014) management in education is no longer the exclusive interest of the "Ivory Tower" experts and specialized research institutes, He notes that it has now become the concern of all training institutions, capacity building agencies, government agencies and schools. Concept of Innovation in Education. Innovation is defined as substantial change in the way of vocational and technical education as practiced in an institution and making it more relevant to the needs of the economy, society and environment (Abraham, 2017). It encourages teachers and students to explore research and use the tools to uncover something new. It brings improvement in to the already stereotyped educational systems as it helps students to use a higher level of thinking in problems solving (Abraham, 2017). Innovation deals with solving a real problem in a fresh and simple way to promote equity and improve learning in an emerging technological and innovating settings.

Historical Perspective of Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria

Technical and vocational education has been in existence before the advent of formal Western education in Nigeria. Attempts were made to develop Nigeria children in various keys such as weaving, sculpturing, blacksmithing, caving, farming, fishing, cattle rearing, hair plaiting, dress-making, leather works, poultry, glass and bead working, catering, dyeing, tinkering and many more. According to Azuoma (2016), traditional education system of the various ethnic groups include; arts and craft of various types have existed as their own expression of vocational training, why traditional agricultural practices had been developed to suit the cultivation of the agricultural species predominantly produced in the different eco geographical areas of the country. The era was emerged by hearing to informed apprenticeship systems. TVET was formalized in the colonial period the Facet TVET in the 1920s, and the number of these institutions grew rapidly in the years leading up to 1960 (Azuoma, 2016). Vocational training was not encouraged in the early part of the colonial era. The origin of vocational and technical education could be traced to the precolonial era when traditional education was practiced. During this era the child was trained in the family trade by direct apprenticeship to either the parents or relations. The conscious planning of the system of technical education in Nigeria dates back to 1946, when it was given a major space in the 10 years plan for development (Nwosu & Micah, 2017). This led to establishment of Yaba Technical Institute in 1947 and several other trade centres in 1952 (Nwosu & Micah, 2017). The Ashby report of 1960 had considerable influence on Nigeria Technical Education and Nigeria Education as a whole by advocating for the introduction of technical subjects in secondary schools learning to the acquisition of a Technical School certificate. There have been visible developments in technical education at all levels in Nigeria with the enhancement of computer technology. Technical and vocational education were assumed to be

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designed for the less privilege and less intellectual ones in the society. Therefore, understanding the effects of technological innovations on students, teachers and schools is critical to developing strategies and techniques to manage and use technology in education. The early schools were built primarily for the purpose of evangelism by the early Christian missionaries, which was characterized by literally type of education tailored towards winning new convert and producing clerks and interpreters (Odionye, Anugom, Nzegbulem & Ojiako, 2015). Before the Yaba College in 1980, the government started to organized some form of vocational training in some departments of government such as lands and survey training school, the Marine training school in 1928 and railway schools in 1931 (Odionye, Anugom, Nzegbulem & Ojiako, 2015). More technical colleges, college of technology, colleges of education (Technical), polytechnics and universities of technology where is publish as a means of ensuring the successful implementation of the then 6 - 3 - 3 - 4 system of education. By 1999, there had been 128 technical colleges, 15 of which were owned by the Federal Government, 101 by the state governments and 12 by private/ religious bodies (Ajayi, 2007). During the same period there 48 polytechnics, 17 of which were owned by the Federal Government, 26 by state governments and 5 by private individuals Ajayi (2007).

Challenges of Technical and Vocational Education and Training TVET Program in Nigeria

Bello and Muhammad (2021) outlined a number of challenges facing technical and vocational education in Nigeria include;

1. Inadequate Funding
2. Negative attitude towards technical and vocational education.
3. Shortage of teaching staff.
4. Lack of continuity in the implementation of policies and practices.
5. Decay in infrastructure in schools.

Curriculum content:

The curricula of vocational and technical education to not provide students with enough technical skills for entrepreneurship but provide them with more in-depth knowledge. To this end, Muoghalu and Ahmad (2023) opined that there is need to address the issue of re - designing vocational and technical programs in Nigeria with the emerging trend in technological innovation to meet our commitments in creating workshops, instructional stimulations, that are relevant to the practice of industrial and commercial activities for viable business engagement. The curriculum content should explicitly provide and state clearly the occupational areas in which vocational skills will be provided.

Poor industrial training:

It is so sad that graduate of vocational and technical education now roam the street is search of White collar jobs because the lack the necessary skills required to be self-reliant or self-employed due to poor training. Technical and Vocational Education students no longer possess the necessary skills as a result of the failure of industrial based supervisors to assist the student in developing the right attitudes in training (Ayonmike, Okwelle & Okeke, 2015). Experience has shown that more of these graduates who are unable to secure paid jobs find it extremely difficult to set up businesses of their own because the lack entrepreneurial skills to do so. Nation is nothing to write home about. Ranging from the poor state of the classrooms to the laboratories are grossly inadequate. Lack of tools and equipment, gross inadequacy of available machines, lack of textbooks and materials are some problems which militated engage vocational and technical education. Hence, it has made the teaching of vocational and technical subjects and courses theoretical than practical. This has left most graduands in these subject areas to be half baked.

Structural Problems:

The structure of vocational and technical education in Nigeria is not balance. Ayonmike, Okwelle and Okeke (2015) identified some of the problems inherent in the structure of vocational and technical education in Nigeria. Non-inclusion of technical subjects in the entry qualification of JAMB and the products of the technical colleges flow into the job market directly because of their limitations in basic science and the structure of not being specific in the learning of technical and teachers at the colleges of education or university. Some Universities do not have such programs or even a department of vocational studies such, the prospective students in the area usually switch to other related discipline. A situation that has almost crippled the course.

Irregular power supply:

This has become the order of the day in Nigeria as most of the colleges do not have generating sets in the event of power failure.

Strategies for Ensuring the Management of Technical and Vocational Education program in Nigeria through Emerging Technologies and Innovations

1. Improved funding of technical and vocational education. Government at the various levels should as a matter of urgent need make adequate funds available for the smooth implementation of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. This would be achieved through increased budgetary provision to the education sub-sector of the Nigeria economy. It is understood that government cannot shoulder it alone, other stakeholders in the Education industry such as parents, community, corporate organization philanthropists, should step up their financial commitment to the provision of vocational and technical education.
2. There should be a change in mindset attitude of auto words vocational and technical education in the country. People should stop saying technical and vocational education as a course that is meant for student from Paul background or less intelligent students.
3. Recruitment of qualified manpower: the government at all levels should employ more qualified and skilled teachers to hand technical and vocational subjects' courses in schools. Also, those other teachers who love the requirement power to carry on should be adequately trained and motivated. This can be achieved by sponsorship teachers to workshop, seminars, conferences and training programmes to position them in the market space.
4. Improved public awareness. This will go a long way to remedy some of the challenges associated with technical and vocational education in Nigeria. Members of the public should give more recognition to graduates of technical education in order to boost the morale of undergraduates in polytechnics and colleges of education technical. This would help parents to push their wards to the department of vocational and technical education.
5. There should be continuity in policies and programs of vocational and technical education. This is very important as somebody causes the political level and not offered at the post graduate level.
6. There should be innovations, regular accreditation and of courses and facilities a technical application on colleges. Most of the laboratories, equipment and classrooms are totally decapitated hence, government should give it a face lift to encourage the student and teachers to study in a conducive atmosphere or scenery environment.
7. Improved curricula contents. The curricula vocational and technical education should be redesigned to provide the required vocational and technical education across the country as this will make the graduates of technical college acquire the necessary jobs skills for the transformation of Nigeria educational system.
8. Effective industrial training should be more effective and encompassing. Also, the inclusion of entrepreneurial skills to compliment the vocational technical skills acquired by the students.
9. There should be provision of world-class facilities in our vocational technical college to enable graduates compete favorably with our counterparts across the globe.
10. Programme restructuring, we go a long way in helping the students achieve educational aim. This can be done by harmonization of a vocational course in the polytechnics, colleges of education technical and universities.
11. There should be regular power supply in our institutions of higher learning to enable teachers and lecturers conduct practical and learn in a conducive environment.

Conclusion

The foregoing discussion has informed us about the place of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. Provision of qualitative technical and vocational education is necessary for technical education to achieve its aim. This can be achieved through improved funding of technical education, change in parental attitude toward vocational education to boost students moral, recruit qualified manpower, improved public esteem, continuity in policies and programmes, renovation of decayed facilities, improved curricular content, effective industrial training, programme restructuring and regular provision of power supply.

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